

Time-Domain Processing to Determine Free-space Antenna Factor

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Abstract— This paper demonstrates the usefulness of time-domain processing to determine free-space antenna factors (FSAF) for electromagnetic compatibility (EMC) antennas. Procedures are explained and data are provided from 30 MHz to 9 GHz. We investigate time gating of dense frequency packed insertion loss data obtained with an ultrawideband measurement system. These results show the advantage of time-domain signal processing to provide reliable results for the free-space antenna factors of EMC antennas.

I. INTRODUCTION

Electromagnetic compatibility (EMC) standards committees, both US national and international, have implemented the use of free-space antenna factors (FSAF) for EMC antennas [1, 2]. The term free-space implies that there is no electrical interaction from the test environment onto the antennas. Present day methods usually involve removing the antennas from any nearby reflecting surface by either raising the antennas to extreme heights on Open Area Test Sites (OATS) or using a large fully anechoic chamber designed for the frequencies of interest. In principle, this concept is a good solution to remove or reduce the offending signal reflections.

We propose the use of technology to provide the same result of removing unwanted signals from the measurement. By applying time-gating to insertion loss data a free-space environment can be mathematically obtained. This concept is not a new one; this use has been discussed several decades earlier [3, 4]. What is new in this paper is the application of this method to determine FSAFs for the EMC community. To demonstrate its effectiveness, this method is applied to data over a wide range of frequencies from 30 MHz to 9 GHz.

II. MEASUREMENT PROCESS

A. Test Procedure in Frequency Domain

The NIST ultrawideband measurement system is shown in Fig. 1, and has been used in other types of applications [5, 6]. The system consists of a set of frequency-specific antennas, a commercially available vector network analyzer, a computer with data collection and processing software, and precision 50 ohm interconnecting cables. In this case, the antennas were the items to be tested. Antennas used for this demonstration were a pair of dual ridged horns (DRG) measured from 1 to 9 GHz, a pair of larger dual ridged horns (large DRG) covering 200 MHz to 2 GHz and a pair of biconical dipoles for 30 to 300 MHz.

The same basic procedure was used for each pair of antennas. First, the antennas were set up on an OATS and the insertion loss data measured in the frequency domain. The measured data were transformed to the time-domain where gating was applied and then the data transformed back to the frequency domain. Finally, the two antenna method [7] and the Friis equation [8] were applied to the time-gated insertion loss data to obtain free-space antenna factors.

For this evaluation, the antennas were placed on towers constructed from low-reflectivity PVC pipe at a height of 5 meters. To study the effects of antenna coupling and site reflections, separation distances of 3, 5, 10 and 20 m were used. The antennas were measured only in the vertical polarization.

CW transmission data (magnitude and phase), S_{21} , were obtained over the antenna pair's frequency range. Measurements were repeated to check the positioning sensitivity of the antenna. Cable and equipment effects were removed with a response calibration prior to measurements and checked after measurements were completed for system thermal stability and connector repeatability.

The frequency step size was set to remove data aliasing in the time-domain. This resulted in small step sizes (less than 500 kHz) and large data files (greater than 45,000 data points). RF cable lengths were minimized by the use of optical links that reduced noise and common mode pickup of RF ambients. These links either transmitted or received the RF power via fiber to minimize signal loss over large distances. A photo of this system is shown in Fig. 2 for a typical setup.

Fig. 1. The NIST ultrawideband measurement system with two typical test antennas.

Fig. 2. Typical setup of the ultrawideband system for free-space antenna factor measurements on the NIST OATS.

B. Data Processing in Time Domain

The data were processed in a multiple-step sequence that readily permitted the separation of the desired propagation events. This time- and frequency-domain processing of densely packed data allows for the efficient manipulation of the OATS transmission loss data to corrected free-space values with environmental effects minimized.

The signal processing sequence used to quantify the desired propagation events is shown in Fig. 3 and is further described in [9]. The procedure can be summarized in four basic steps:

1. Inverse Fourier transform CW magnitude and phase data, S_{21} , to obtain a time-domain data waveform.
2. Time gate the insertion loss waveform to emphasize the direct antenna-to-antenna coupling and suppress propagation from any nearby scatterers.
3. Fourier transform the time-gated waveform of step 2 back to CW magnitude and phase data, S_{21} .
4. Process this time-gated CW insertion loss data using the two-antenna method and Friis equation to determine the free-space antenna factors.

To find the FSAF we used Eqn 24 from [7]:

$$AF = 10 \cdot \log\left(\frac{F}{d}\right) + \frac{1}{2} [IL + Corr - 16.0] \quad (1)$$

with $Corr = 0$ for free space. The insertion loss term (IL) was replaced with the time-gated value obtained from the time-domain signal processing:

$$IL = |FT \{ IL_{gated} \}| \quad (2)$$

where FT denotes the Fourier transform of the enclosed term.

This term is now just the directly coupled signal after the reflected data were removed through time-domain processing. We have neglected the contributions of internal antenna reflections and cable reflections, and assumed the radiation aperture is known.

Fig. 3. Signal Processing sequence to obtain free-space insertion loss data.

III. MEASUREMENT RESULTS

A. Determination of the Time Gate

Determination of the time gate was essential in obtaining clean and accurate results. Errors can occur when too much of the data waveform has been truncated. Familiarity with the antenna impulse response characteristics and experimentation with different gate times are critical to minimize this error. Figs 4(a-c) show time-domain waveforms of the three antennas measured at different separations. Nominal times used for gating in this investigation are given in Table 1. Ray-tracing was used as a check of the direct and ground plane reflected paths. These path times provide an indication where these two signals might overlap and are given in Table 2. A ratio of one nanosecond per foot was used.

Upon examining Figs 4(a-c), it can be seen that the high-frequency DRG has a fairly clean antenna waveform for all the distances measured, due to its relatively short ring-down time. However, the analysis for the two lower frequency antennas is not so simple. Longer ring-down times cause the direct and ground reflected signal waveforms to overlap at the longer separation distances. This required a slight shortening of the time gates for these configurations to obtain usable time-gated data, but with slightly larger errors. The biconicals also exhibited an additional time delay when compared to the

TABLE I
ANTENNA RING-DOWN GATING TIMES

Antenna	Time (nS)
Biconical dipole	15-22
large DRG	10-20
DRG	6-8

TABLE II

USEFUL DIRECT AND GROUND REFLECTED PATH TIMES

Antenna Setup Geometry	Direct Path (nS)	Ground Reflected Path (nS)
D = 3 m, h=5 m	9.8	34.2
D = 5 m, h=5 m	16.4	36.7
D = 10 m, h=5 m	32.8	46.4
D = 20 m, h=5 m	65.6	73.3

Fig. 4. (a) Time-domain waveforms for the DRG antennas, (b) for the large DRG antennas, and (c) for the biconical antennas.

anticipated values. This additional delay is most likely due to its internal cabling and balun network.

B. Results of applying Time Gating

Once the insertion data were time-gated and Fourier transformed back to the frequency domain, they were used to find the FSAF of these antennas. The Friis equation was applied and the antenna factor (AF) determined. The differences due to the various distances and between the gated and ungated data for each antenna were investigated. Fig. 5(a) and Fig. 5(b) show the differences for the DRG; Fig. 6(a) and Fig. 6(b) are for the biconicals. For brevity, the results obtained for the large DRG data are not shown here. The difference data were normalized to the average of the gated data for each antenna to emphasize the differences.

All three antennas exhibited similar improvements in reproducibility with removal of the reflected signals. The DRG shows the best clustering due to its relatively short pulse waveform. The biconical shows the largest spread of repeatability. This is most likely due to its long pulse waveform and the non-ideal time gating applied to the data at the larger distances. The ungated biconical data show the expected nulls from ground bounce across frequency.

The biconical data were also compared to the near free-space values used in [1]. The modeled 3 meter free-space insertion loss was used to determine AF. As shown in Fig 6(b) the modeled data compare well to the measured gated values.

Fig. 5. Comparison of (a) ungated and (b) gated AF differences for the DRG antenna.

Fig. 6. Comparison of (a) un-gated and (b) gated AF differences for the biconical antenna. Note the significant reduction of errors achieved through time gating.

Two additional benefits from the time-domain processing are an apparent lower system noise floor and the suppression of RF ambient effects. As seen in Fig. 7, there is about a 20-30 dB reduction in these signals. Even the spurious FM and cell phone band signals have been reduced.

Fig. 7. Reduction of noise floor levels by use of time gating.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

The use of time-domain signal processing for determining free-space antenna factors for several EMC antennas has been outlined. Results for the different separation distances are compared. Valid results depend highly on valid time-gating to allow for the full direct signal waveform while removing the reflected signals. Reliable and repeatable data can be obtained using this method.

Separation of the direct and ground reflected waveforms provide a unique perspective for this evaluation. Items that affect the outcome of this method include the ring-down time of the antenna and the relation of the direct to the reflected path times. These conditions are favorable when the ring-down time is relatively short compared to the difference in the direct to reflected path times. Favorable conditions allow for improved accuracy in the determination of free-space antenna factors.

Additional work is needed in this area. Planned topics to explore include more measurement comparisons at lower heights and additional distances; measurement in the horizontal polarization; and inclusion of additional antennas. The use of RF absorber to reduce the ground reflections will also be studied. Finally, modeling of the various antennas in the multiple configurations will be compared to the measured data, where appropriate.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The authors thank P. Wilson and M. Kelly for their support and encouragement with this EMC standards related effort.

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